

Galaxy Clusters around $z \sim 1-2$

Low Luminosity Radio Galaxies

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Radio morphologies. Fanaroff & Riley (1974) classification

FRI

FRII

Zirbel (1996)

- FRI: Jet decelerates to $v \ll c$ at ~ 1 kpc
- FRII: Relativistic jet on scales ~ 100 kpc up to ~ 1 Mpc
- FRI / FRII divide: $L_{178 \text{ MHz}} < 10^{26} \text{ W Hz}^{-1}$

Local FRIs

- ◆ **“starved quasar”**: faint optical nuclear emission (Chiaberge et al. 1999, Leiptzki et al. 2009, Baldi et al. 2010)
- ◆ Host galaxy: mainly **giant elliptical (cD)** with the most massive BHs (Donzelli et al. 2007, Zirbel & Baum 1997)
- ◆ **~70% of them in rich clusters**, at variance with FRIIs (Hill & Lilly 1991; Zirbel 1997; Wing & Blanton 2011)

Local FRIs and clusters

90% of Abell clusters host a radio galaxies,
94% of them are FRIs (Ledlow & Owen 1996)

Perseus Cluster $D \sim 75$ Mpc --- Fabian et al. (2011), Blackbird obs.

High-z FRIs

- ◆ **Two FRIs at $z \sim 1$** (Snellen & Best 2001)
- ◆ **~ 30 FRI candidates at $z \sim 1-2$** (Chiaberge et al. '09)

FRIIs at $z \sim 1-2$. Why?

Clusters

- **Signspots of HIGH-z CLUSTERS**
- **Link between $z > \sim 2$ protoclusters and clusters**
(review: Overzier 2016)
- **Protoclusters have large reservoirs of molecular gas. What's their fate?**
(Webb+2017, Noble+2017, Statch+17, Hayashi+17)
- Formation and evolution of the **red sequence**
- **AGN feedback vs. cooling flows**

AGN

- Hints for strong **cosmological evolution** up to $z \sim 1.0$ (Sadler et al., 2007, Smolcic et al. 2009, McAlpine et al. 2013)
- Formation and evolution of the **most massive galaxies and BHs**
- **Feedback**: BH accretion – environment (Ineson et al. 2015)

The sample

- **FRI**s candidates at $z \sim 1-2$ (Chiaberge et al. 2009, C09)
- **COSMOS** (2sq degrees)
- Mainly based on **radio (FIRST) and optical selection**, NOT on redshifts

Redshifts

- **Accurate redshifts** (Baldi et al. 2013) are required to **redefined the sample in radio power**
- **Few spectroscopic-z**: zCOSMOS bright (Lilly et al. 2007), Magellan (Trump et al. 2007)
- **Photo-z**: SED modeling includes stellar and dust emission

Distant Cluster search techniques

- ★ **SZ effect**, only a few at $z > 1$ (e.g. Planck coll. XXIX 2013; Hasselfield et al. 2013, Reichardt et al. 2013)
- ★ **X-ray** (Rosati et al. 2002, Wang et al. 2016) ; $I_o = I_e(1+z)^{-4}$
- ★ **Photo-z and number counts** (Eisenhardt et al. 2008; Knobel 2009, 2012; Bellagamba et al. 2017)
- ★ **Planck – Herschel** (Clements et al., 2013)
- ★ **Color selection** (e.g. Gladders & Yee 2005; Papovich 2008).
Red-sequence is just forming between $z \sim 1-2$ (Hilton et al. 2010; Fassbender et al. 2011; Santos et al. 2011)
- ★ **Search around radio galaxies** (Miley & De Breuck 2008, Galametz et al. 2012, Wylezalek+2013, Paterno-Mahler et al. 2016)

powerful (and rare) FRIs are commonly adopted

Motivations for a new method

- **High- z clusters are difficult to detect with existing methods**

(only ~ 15 spectroscopically confirmed $z > \sim 1.5$ clusters, see Tozzi et al. 2013 and refs. therein, e.g. Papovich+2010, Cooke et al. 2016, Wang et al. 2016 ...)

- **Methods based on photo- z and number counts** (Scoville+2013 and ref. therein) **affected by:**

- 1) low number counts
- 2) increasing photo- z uncertainties
- 3) photo- z catastrophic failure at $z > \sim 1.5$ (redshift desert)

Poisson Probability Method (PPM). How does it work?

Castignani et al. (2014a, ApJ, 792, 113)

PPM, how does it work?

PPM plots

3.5σ detection

PPM plots

spectroscopic confirmation ($z=2.45$, Diener+2015)

2.5σ detection

Overdensity detections

Castignani et al. (2014b, ApJ, 792, 114)

- The overdensities found within the FRI redshifts uncertainties are associated with the radio galaxy.*

22/32 →

69 ± 8%

Six
overdensities at
 $z > 1.5$

...in agreement with what found locally (Zirbel 1997)

...higher than what found for FRIs at similar redshifts (Galamez et al. 2012, Wylezalek et al. 2013)

Gravitational arc in the field of COSMOS-FRI 01!!

Figure: HST ACS image of the field of COSMOS-FRI 01

Independent confirmation for some of our $z \sim 1$ cluster candidates found in catalogs of X-ray (Finoguenov+07) or spectroscopically (Knobel+09,12) selected clusters

Search for CO in z=0.9 LLRGs with 30mt IRAM

CO(4-3) Upper limits

$SCO < 3 \text{ Jy km/s} \rightarrow LCO < 8e+09 \text{ pc}^2 \cdot \text{K} \cdot \text{km/s} \rightarrow M_{\text{H2}} < 2e+09 \text{ Msun}$
 (GC, Combes, Salomé et al., in prep.)

(SEDs : Baldi+13)

Left : Optical (HST,ACS) – Right : radio (COSMOS FIRST) (Chiaberge +2009)

Main results and conclusions

(high-z galaxy clusters and RGs)

- **~70% FRIs are in clusters or rich groups, as found locally (rate higher than that of powerful FRIIs)**

- **FRIs+PPM → valuable alternative to existing methods to search for $z \sim 1-2$ galaxy clusters**

~ 10^7 LLRGs hosting $z \sim 1-2$ galaxy clusters and rich groups at the time SKA+Euclid+LSST will be operational